

**work
in
progress**

2002

no. 13

**DEPARTMENT OF ENGLISH
AHMADU BELLO UNIVERSITY
ZARIA, NIGERIA**

PUBLISHED IN ASSOCIATION
WITH ONIS EXCEL PUBLISHING

ISSN: **0795-2848**

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CONTENTS

Akuso, Ezekiel

Brathwaite and The Search For A
Poetic Technique In "Masks" (*The Arrivants*)..... 1

Babajo, Ahmed Kofar

Recent Developments in
The Short Story Form In Northern Nigeria 16

Ayegba, Martins Adegbe

Beyond Rhetoric: Communicating Democracy
Through Drama And Theatre (*An Evaluation of
a TFD Workshop On Democracy and
Good Governance In Borno State*) 26

Menegbe, Awam David

Factors Militating Against the Implementation of
Drama In Education In Kogi State, Nigeria 44

Ofuokwu, 'Dili

New Englishes As Models for Educational Purposes 54

Imenyi, Imoh Abang

Dialogism And The Dramatic Genre: Deconstructing
Mikchail Bakhtin's Theory Of The Novel67

Abah, Edward Ochigbo

Repositioning Gender In The African American Narrative: A
Study Of Toni Morrison's *Beloved*..... 80

Ekpeme, Ode Johnson

A Psycholinguistic Consideration of
The Relationship Between The Average
Memory Span In A Child And Sentence Patterns 91

Ibileye, Gbenga Solomon

“Talking” On The Wall:

The Discourse Structure Of Graffiti

101

Buhari Sekula, Halima

Woman's Body As Sexual Object: A Study Of

Wole Soyinka's *The Lion And The Jewel*

111

Abah, James

Criminalization Of Power And Demonization

Of Victims: Soyinka's *The Beatification Of Area*

Boy..... 122

Lucas, Joseph Mbachu

Content Packaging For Mass Communication Transactions In

Nigeria: Challenges And Prospects. 133

Amodu, Jonah Enejoh

Language Of Advertisement: A Pragmatic Analysis Of

Commercial Adverts In The Print Media 143

Musa, Rasheed Abiodun

Democratic Direction And The Aesthetics Of

Military Theatre In Nigeria 154

Omokore, Sade O

Nigerian Women Writers And The Short Story:

A Study Of *Breaking The Silence* 178

Idegu, Emmy Unuja

Aspects Of Change And Continuity In

The Qgani Festival Performance Of Igalaland 190

Gani-Ikilama, Taiwo Olufunto

Pluralisation In English: Morpho-Phonological Realisations And

Redundancy 202

Liman, Abubakar Aliyu	
.Harmeneutics Between Metaphysics And Artistic Vision In Soyinka's <i>The Credo Of Being And Nothingness</i> 211
Liman, Rasheedah	
Identity Construction And The Evolution Of African-American Consciousness.	220
Omale, Hilda Ojonoma	
Reading Competence: A Necessity For Content Area Learning 231
Abubakar, Tanimu	
De-Scribing The Subaltern Space: Black South African Short Story And National Racism Since Sharpeville	239
Odiwo, Keston Aliyu	
Disillusionment and Political Struggle In the novels of MejaMwangi	270

ASPECTS OF CHANGE AND CONTINUITY IN THE OGANI FESTIVAL PERFORMANCE OF I GALALAND

IDEGU, EMMY UNUJA

INTRODUCTION

Most indigenous festival performances in Africa have not remained the same since their contact with foreign cultures and with foreign systems of government. Most often, the ruling class has exerted a towering influence on these festivals towards incorporating the people's performances to suit the demands and aspirations of the government. This paper appraises the societal influence on Ogani festival performance in Igalaland of Kogi State of Nigeria and ascertains the inevitability of this incursion and the challenges thereof.

African festival performances undergo several levels of changes because of the dynamic nature of the society in which the festivals are performed and, of course, the changing status of the performers. Apart from the avowed influence of Christianity and Islam on these festival performances, various govenwients at all levels have also continuously exerted influence and control over festival performances to their own advantage. Festivals that are typically sacred and ritual based, lose their original spiritual and scared essence and become mere entertainment tools the moment governments get involved. This is solely because they are aborted from their natural settings, obliterated from the normal due process in stages of performance and even sometimes denied of their original performers.

Ogani festival is performed in Igalaland to celebrate the military might of the Igala kingdom in their successful war of liberation from the socio-political dominance and control of the Jukuns (in present day Taraba State) sometime in the early fifteenth century. The Igala people before the said war of independence were a vassal state to the Jukuns. Ogani festival came into being in Igalaland to commemorate the victory of the

Igala people in the said war of liberation from the Jukuns. The festival, which has lasted for almost six centuries, is till date celebrated annually and strictly by the Hausa settlers, the owners of the festival. The festival features songs, music and dance, spectacle, beautiful costumes and props, and its celebration is usually a time to reflect on the heroic battle against the Jukuns and the need to continuously maintain internal peace in Igalaland.

Because of the socio-cultural contact of Ogani performers and other members of the society within which the festival is celebrated (and even outside its immediate environment), the festival has undergone some changes, Kalu (1978:5) rationalises this change of a people's culture and behaviour when he writes that,

Customs and traditions are not static; they are modified or changed entirely as a result of deliberate actions or as a result of interactions with other customs and traditions.

The challenge for the Ogani festival is not just the politics of cultural interactions but the extent to which such interrelatedness augurs well for the owners of the festival vis-a-vis its intended functionality to the community that owns the performance.

Changing faces of the Ogani festival celebration.

The Language of Performance.

One of the areas of changes in the Ogani festival is the language of performance. The language of communication at the inception of Ogani festival in Igalaland was Hausa, during and after the Ogani festival celebration. This is because the festival was “imported” to Igalaland by the invited Hausa Islamic scholars with whose prayer support the Igala people won the war against the Jukuns. Today, the language of communication is almost entirely Igala. The influence of the Igala culture over the performance has also led to some noticeable changes not only in the form of performance, but also in the audiences' response to the contents of the Ogani celebration in recent times. Because of this overbearing influence of the Igala language and culture, it is difficult to suggest a continuity of the original language of Hausa, for after all; the

Hausa settlers have themselves been greatly incorporated into the host Igala culture. The Ogani festival cannot therefore live unaffected by the dominant Igala culture. This also goes for the appreciable influence of the Hausa culture on the Igala people inherent in intermarriages and limited participation in the Ogani festival celebration by the host community. Because it was the Hausa settlers that introduced Islamic faith in Igalaland, the influence of this faith on the Igala people is reflected in some level of followership of Islam as a religion in Igalaland.

Satire

Satire plays a very prominent role in the Ankpa Ogani performance. The Ogani singer uses this genre to check societal ills by castigating the vicious and for commending the virtuous. The society, aware of his laudable role, grants the Ogani satirist a kind of immunity. This is what Okwori in his paper "The Performer in African Society" observes about performers in Idoma society, when he writes that,'

This immunity is supposed to protect them from molestation or harassment in the discharge of their duties of policing the society, lampooning and castigating anti-social behaviour. Due to this artistic license, they can satirize, overtly criticize or harangue the policies of elders or the village heads and other characters.

In the ideal Ogani festival performance, this was what operated. But times have changed. People have now become more enlightened and aware of their rights; thus, some members of the community no longer take this part of the festival with the old attitude of fun. Today, some Ogani singers who dare satirize people are dragged to the police station. This sometimes leads to court cases where fundamental human rights activists and those learned in the interpretation of law, settle scores with the tradition of Ogani festival which hitherto, was given no interpretation of slander, character assassination or defamation but was regarded solely as corrective, and a vibrant social regulation organ.

Under this new dispensation, the Ogani satirist's role is curtailed and inevitably censored. In some cases, he no longer calls characters ridiculed by their real names as he emphasizes in this powerful descriptive portrayal to know whoever is the subject of attack. This protest is typical of the new artist-society relationship. For the Ogani singer, these relationships may be characterized at times either by harmony and agreement or acceptance of fault by the victim and subsequent change of character for the better, or as in the case of some recent instances, traces of protests and legal battles.

Government Interference.

Another significant change in Ogani festival is evident in the Angwa Ogebe group at Ankpa. This group is now registered with the State government. Because of this, they no longer perform with other Angwa descendents in and around Ankpa and neither do they adhere to the traditional performance period of the month of Maulud. By this development, the Angwa Ogebe Ogani performers no longer perform in conformity with the thirty-day period, during which the various stages of Ogani at Ankpa, are undergone. Instead of the customary stages of the festival celebrations, they only perform the acrobatic and dancing aspects of the festival at the beck and call of the state government, especially to entertain guests. It is believed that their action is in line with the state government's directives that all social organisations be duly registered with her. Consequently because of this new Angwa Ogebe Ogani festival performance, they now enjoy government recognition and sponsorship for competitions in arts and culture festivals.

The Angwa Ogebe Ogani performers' "rebellion" can be explained in what Benjamin (1969:221) terms, the "tremendous shattering of tradition and the liquidation of the traditional value of the cultural heritage" of the people. At the end of the day, the eliminated elements in this Ogani performance by the Angwa Ogebe group is its aura, which withers, making it similar to ritual

that loses its potency and sacredness when turned to mere entertainment.

The Angwa Ogebe Ogani festival, due to this recent development, has got its significance in the society limited, and the performance clearly polarized into two groups. While some performers are loyal to the state government, others remain culturally independent of state influence. In this polarization the group which still upholds its cultural essence, but nevertheless embellishes this essence with social regulation, falls into traditional institutions similar to what Williams (1977:122) tags the residual, which, by definition,

... has been effectively formed in the past but it is still active in the cultural process, not only... as an element of the past, but as an effective element of the present,

On the other hand, the group which has deviated from its original function of a religious nature into purely social significance belongs to the category that Williams (*ibid*: 123) christens the emergent which he views as that with

... new meanings, values new practices, new relationships and this kind of relationships are continually being created.

Here, Angwa Ogebe Ogani performance is coordinated and sponsored by the government for social engagements giving little or no significance to the basic cultural values and guidelines of the festival. With this present relationship with the government, the Angwa Ogebe Ogani singer and performer can no longer bring out the shortcomings of the government as they used to do. Satire on or about political leaders, especially government functionaries, is put aside and the emphasis has now shifted from the unity of all Angwa descendants during Ogani celebration to unity, and solidarity of performances in honour of government social engagements. This practice has a lot of implications because,

To the extent that it emerges, and especially to the degree that it is oppositional..., the process of ... incorporation significantly begins. (*Ibid*: 125)

Angwa Ogebe group of Ogani performers is now oppositional to the other Ogani performers, considering its stance with the government. The awareness of the implications of this government involvement in the people's culture of performance is hidden from their comprehension. Williams (Ibid: 125) rightly observes that, "much incorporation looks like recognition, acknowledgement and thus, a form of acceptance" by the government. No wonder, the Angwa Ogebe group now sees and considers their new brand of Ogani performance as superior to the other Angwa descendants'. In this antagonistic posture there have been regular clashes and conflicts of ideas between the residual and the emergent Ogani festival celebrants. This government influence affects the sum-total of the cultural potency of the Ogani festival performers.

Darah (1993:6) agrees with this assertion when he observes that culture is

...a way of life of a given society or people, the natural inheritance of man consisting of the natural things which are expressions of man's ideas, his art and sciences, and philosophy of life.

The Angwa Ogebe Ogani performers' inheritance, as far as the natural mode of expressing themselves through this festival is concerned, is under a serious threat of extinction because of government influence. It should be emphasised however, that to a certain extent, the impetus for government interference is supplied by some Ogani performers' desire to gain relevance by the government.

These changes and developments in Ogani notwithstanding, the performers are still Angwa descendants, or inhabitants. No matter the knowledge of the festival by the Igala hosts, they still stand excluded from active participation in this festival beyond spectatoiship This is an aspect of the festival that has so far stood the test of time.

Implications of government involvement in Ogani festival celebration Fanon (1969:189) observes that no one can truly wish for the spread of African culture if he does not give practical support to the creation of the conditions necessary to the existence of that culture. Based on this premise, it would appear on the face of it that the state government is aiding cultural development. However, the state government's involvement in the Angwa Ogebe Ogani performance is definitely not an attempt to promote and advance the people's culture, but a step, as it were, at incorporating the people's festival into the dominant ruling system. Angwa Ogebe Ogani performers no longer bring into the open through satire and ridicule the pitfalls of the government of which they are now a part.

In his paper, "Hegemony and cultural imperialism; toward a historical re-evolution of African Literature", Nasidi contends that colonialism,

... created a new order, it created new men. To penetrate the colonized meant that their whole cultural system has to be violently relegated in status, marginalized or even totally negated. Henceforth the savage would be speechless. To speak he must now rely on his conqueror's language and modes of signification. To function in the new world order he would rely on his master's voice.

Nasidi in this paper focuses attention on white colonialists. Within the context of Ogani festival, it is no longer the white colonialists that threaten its existence, but the state government, whose language and voice the Ogani Angwa Ogebe performer must now use, obey and project.

By this act, the state government is not at all helping to preserve the Ogani festival, but incorporating it; not reviving it, but helping it to maintain their (government's) lead as the dominant ruling class, even in people's cultural festival performances. This move is desperately political, not entirely cultural preservation and

acknowledgement. By transposing the Ogani festival into the purely aesthetic, it is made rife for incorporation into the consumer culture of tourism. Under such conditions, the Ogani performers are used as a tool by the government in the same way as the then U.S.S.R. used her mass culture for propaganda and pedagogy, upholding political beliefs and strengthening the maintenance of Russian political domination.

•Vansina (1997:39) writing about performances and the relevance of the venue and time, records that,

Performances are not produced at random times. The occasions for performances are limited. They are inspired by practical rules of traditions. Many rituals containing historical messages are performed when appropriate. Each sort of tradition has its appropriate occasions for performance.

By the involvement of government in the Ogani Angwa Ogebe celebrations, the rules of the traditions guarding the festival as observed above are ignored. May be unknown to the people, as the government begins to have some towering influence in the Ogani Angwa Ogebe performances, the relationship between them and the government will not be that of the leaf and branch, but rather that of the caterpillar and the poor leaf. The governments will, no doubt, use the people's performance culture, which was a spontaneous autochthonous expression of the people; shaped by people themselves and to suit their own needs. The government's embrace of Ogani may therefore be regarded as sucking the performance into its mass culture and it therefore ceases to be wholly the people's cultural expression.

The government does this because, according to Okwori (1987:142),

The ruling class is aware of the potency and appeal of these performances to the people. They know that to make an impression on the people and reach them, they must seek means with which the people will identify. Thus, they resort to using the performance forms of the people to sell their values while creating the belief that they are advancing the culture of the people.

In the final analysis, the state is only taking over the artistic form of the people, but misappropriating them in such a way as to preach values, which sustain the government. As the Angwa Ogebe Ogani performer and his art, which hitherto molded, mirrored, and expressed the collective will of the society as well as steered the wheel of its development now drifts into oblivion, the socio-cultural and functional role of the performer and his art becomes limited.

Expressing her feelings on a similar societal influence on the Ebre dance in Ibibioland, Ufford in Okwori (2002:147) asserts that,

The traditional Ibibio society associates dance with virtue because no one with questionable character could dance before the people. Today, it is sad to note that the reverse is the case. The identity of the Ibibio woman in dance has been so distorted and abused because of foreign influences. The traditional performances are removed from their original context because of many reasons; the commercialization of these performances and the influences of colonial/western education and aesthetics.

To leave the Angwa Ogebe Ogani performance in its original form will only make it a museum piece in so far as it is not relating to the changing society. Ogani needs to undergo changes so as to maintain its relevance to the society. However, it is the direction and the manner of this change that poses threat and challenge. The Angwa Ogebe Ogani performers are so glad that their performances sometimes come on air through the electronic media, suggesting government recognition and their arrival on the scene of the government-approved culture of tourism. They have also been conditioned to accept that their new form is better than the old. Such is the power of incorporation by the dominant ruling class. This change is consequently not in the right direction or in favour of the performers. The Ogani festival can change, but such changes should be made to benefit those who own it, those who

engage in the performance. The people can benefit through the use of artistic forms in the festival to sell relevant and useful information to the populace, to engage their everyday problems, to educate them and to make them find workable solutions to the problems and contradictions of their daily lives.

CONCLUSION

No doubt, the Ogani festival plays significant socio-cultural roles within the society of its celebrations. The Igala people are known to stage festivals in honour of gods, dead heroes and commemorate important historical events in their life. It is not surprising therefore, that the Ogani festival emerged in Igalaland in memory of victories. The celebrations keep fresh in the people's collective and communal mind their past historic and cultural values even as it plays the social regulation role. The coming into being of the Ogani festival in Igalaland paved the way for cultural exchange between the original Angwa settlers who were Hausa speaking from Bebeji-Kano, and the Igala people. Through this, the two parties have been able to understand and value each other's culture and tradition to the extent that today, there are only negligible areas of difference between the Angwa descendants and the Igala people. The influence of the dominant Igala culture and tradition over the Hausa Angwa settlers is evident in the Ogani festival, and the settlers' way of life.

Ogani has undergone a lot of changes. Though some of these have had little or no negative effects on the festival and its performances, the magnitude of its recent changes is more evident in government participation in the celebration of this festival. This, we argue, limits the efficacy of the festival's significance as the people's cultural event. Government involvement in the festival becomes questionable when the people's performance and culture are turned into mere spectacle, and stripped of its cultural setting and the opportunity to make critical comments about unpopular policies of the government. The government can instead use the performance to bring her people into the centre of national consciousness.

There is the need for one to look into the positive aspects of our traditional festivals, which can be used for national unity,

understanding and development without de-emphasising the cultural values attached to such festivals. The Ogani festival, with its wide coverage of Igalaland and parts of Plateau State, is one of the possible avenues towards attaining the elusive national unity. The writer's observation about the changing status of the Ogani festival is not meant to frown at change but to encourage a careful look at the cultural dynamics of the people and as it affects or influences the festival and its changing operational modes.

Finally, the significance of the Ogani festival is made more glaring as it assumes a structure of collective mobilization. As the isolated and emotional responses of single individuals are pulled and collectively directed through Ogani performance, the sum- total of the performers' and the people's cultural values and societal norms are evaluated, understood and accepted. The characteristic features of the festival can thus be summed up to include a marked desire to associate by means of musical performances, dances, prayers between persons, the gods and the spirits of the ancestors, and with the life of the community. Through this, the community ensures the continuity of its existence. Herein lies one of the reasons why, despite areas of differences in the Ogani festival celebrations in Igalaland and some changes in the performance, its role as a binding and unifying force should remain intact.

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